

Redox Reactions in Non-Aqueous Media : Determination of Xanthates and Dithiocarbamates with N-Bromosuccinimide

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N-Bromosuccinimide solution in acetonitrile has been used as an oxidant for the direct visual and potentiometric determination of alkali metal xanthates and dithiocarbamates in the presence of potassium iodide in acetonitrile medium. In visual titrations, the end-point is signalled by the appearance of distinct and permanent yellow colouration due to iodine by the first drop of oxidant solution in excess. Potentiometric titrations are performed using antimony or modified-calomel as reference electrodes and a bright platinum wire as an indicator electrode. The methods described are simple, accurate and widely applicable.

THE usefulness of non-aqueous redox methods for the determination of compounds which are slightly soluble in water or react with it through hydrolysis or oxidation is well established. The scope of such methods can be further extended to the analysis of compounds which tend to react with the media i. e., acids, bases etc. of aqueous redox titrations.

Xanthates and dithiocarbamates have considerable industrial, medicinal and agricultural importance. The determination of these compounds is therefore of great interest and scope. In spite of the tendency of xanthates and dithiocarbamates to be easily oxidised to the corresponding dixanthogens and thiurum disulphides, redox methods have not been extensively used for the determination of these compounds. This is due to the tendency of these compound to undergo decomposition with acids which serve as the media of a variety of redox titrations. The determination of these compounds in non-aqueous media is therefore of great value.

N-Bromosuccinimide has found quite a large number of applications as an oxidimetric reagent in aqueous (acidic, alkaline or buffered) media. Regarding the determination of xanthates and dithiocarbamates with this oxidant, the only attempt in this direction is due to Sarwar et al² who titrated some xanthates with N-bromosuccinimide in aqueous buffered (pH 4) solutions in the presence of potassium iodide. The end-point was marked by the appearance of blue colour. No efforts appear to have been made to use the reagent for the determination of xanthates in non-aqueous media ; and of dithiocarbonates in aqueous or non-aqueous media. The present communication reports the use of N-bromosuccinimide as an oxidimetric reagent in non-aqueous (acetonitrile) medium. The reagent has been employed for the visual and potentiometric determination of xanthates and dithiocarbamates in acetonitrile medium in the presence of potassium iodide. Xanthates and dithiocarbamates are oxidised to the corresponding dixanthogens and thiurum disulphides.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents : Potentiometric titrations were performed with 'OSAW CROMPTON' potentiometer using 'OSAW SPOT REFLECTING' galvanometer, antimony or modified-calomel (methanol saturated with potassium chloride used instead of aqueous potassium chloride) reference electrode and a bright platinum wire indicator electrode.

Acetonitrile : Distilled from P₂O₅ twice (5g/litre).

N-Bromosuccinimide, 0.05N in acetonitrile. The standard solution was prepared by dissolving a little more than the calculated amount of recrystallised sample of the compound in acetonitrile. The solution was standardised iodometrically in aqueous medium.

Xanthates : Prepared by mixing equimolar quantities of the corresponding alcohols, potassium hydroxide (dissolved in minimum quantity of water) and carbon disulphide, at temperature below 10°. The compounds were recrystallised by dissolving in acetone and precipitating with petroleum ether (b. p. 40°-60°).

Dithiocarbamates : Commercial product (diethyl dithiocarbamate) or prepared by reported methods^{3,4}.

The purity of xanthates and dithiocarbamates was checked by known methods.

Potassium iodide : One percent (w/v) solution in acetonitrile.

All other reagents were of guaranteed quality.

Procedure : Aliquots of solutions of each compound in acetonitrile were taken in a titration vessel and mixed with 2 ml of one percent potassium iodide solution in acetonitrile. Each solution was diluted to 20 to 25 ml with acetonitrile, cooled to room temperature (25°) and titrated visually and potentiometrically with standard (0.05N) N-bromosuccinimide solution (in acetonitrile) run from a microburette provided with guard tube for the protection of oxidant solution from atmospheric

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moisture. In visual titrations, the end-point was detected by the appearance of yellow tint imparted to the solution by the first drop of oxidant solution in excess.

The potentiometric titrations were performed by using antimony or modified-calomel electrode as reference electrode and a bright platinum wire as indicator electrode. The solutions were magnetically stirred during potentiometric titrations. A sharp jump in potential was observed at the equivalence point in each titration. In Figure 1a are shown the

potentiometric titration curves of potassium ethyl xanthate and sodium diethyl dithiocarbamate as typical of the set of xanthates and dithiocarbamates using platinum wire as indicator electrode and antimony electrode as reference electrode. The same using platinum wire as indicator electrode but modified-calomel electrode as reference electrode are shown in Figure 1b.

From the volume of standard (0.05N) N-bromosuccinimide solution used corresponding to the end-point in each titration, the amount of each compound was calculated. Results are recorded in Table I.

Fig. 1.

Potassium ethyl xanthate—○—○—○—○—○—○—
 Sodium diethyl dithiocarbamate—□—□—□—□—□—

TABLE I—TITRATIONS OF XANTHATES AND DITHIOCARBAMATES WITH STANDARD (0.05N) N-BROMOSUCCINIMIDE IN ACETONITRILE

Compound	Amount found ⁺ , mg		Amount found ⁺⁺ , mg	
	Mean*, standard deviation(±) Visual Method	Potentiometric Method	Mean*, standard deviation(±) Visual Method	Potentiometric Method
Xanthates (potassium salts)				
Ethyl	10.06(0.039)	10.03(0.032)	40.18(0.081)	40.14(0.052)
iso-Propyl	9.95(0.032)	9.97(0.031)	39.86(0.072)	39.88(0.048)
n-Propyl	10.04(0.026)	10.02(0.024)	40.12(0.054)	40.10(0.042)
iso-butyl	9.96(0.027)	9.98(0.022)	39.81(0.075)	39.86(0.051)
n-Butyl	9.98(0.025)	10.01(0.016)	39.91(0.062)	39.92(0.038)
n-Amyl	9.94(0.041)	9.95(0.035)	39.84(0.058)	39.88(0.047)
Dithiocarbamates (sodium salts)				
Methyl	9.94(0.028)	9.95(0.027)	40.14(0.082)	40.11(0.054)
Ethyl	10.07(0.031)	10.04(0.029)	39.90(0.068)	39.92(0.046)
n-Propyl	10.08(0.036)	10.05(0.024)	40.16(0.076)	40.15(0.051)
iso-Propyl	9.96(0.027)	9.98(0.026)	39.84(0.074)	39.90(0.049)
Dimethyl	10.05(0.038)	10.03(0.034)	40.23(0.087)	40.16(0.057)
Diethyl	9.97(0.024)	9.98(0.021)	40.12(0.075)	40.10(0.044)

+ Amount of each compound taken, 10mg.

++ Amount of each compound taken, 40mg.

* Mean of 10 determinations.

Results and Discussion

In all potentiometric titrations performed with either modified-calomel or antimony electrode as reference electrode and bright platinum wire as indicator electrode, the potentials attained stable values immediately on addition of each instalment of the oxidant. A sharp jump in potential of the order of 70 to 120 mV (for xanthates) and 240 to 285 mV (for dithiocarbamates) per 0.05 ml of 0.05N oxidant solution was observed at the equivalence point using platinum-modified calomel electrode assembly. Using platinum-antimony electrode assembly, however, the jump in potential was of the order of 250 to 300 mV (for xanthates) and 340 to 420 mV (for dithiocarbamates) with the addition of 0.05 ml of 0.05N oxidant solution. The results recorded under potentiometric method in Table I have been obtained using platinum-antimony electrode assembly.

It is evident from Table I that xanthates (potassium ethyl xanthate, potassium iso-propyl xanthate, potassium n-propyl xanthate, potassium iso-butyl xanthate, potassium n-butyl xanthate and potassium n-amyl xanthate) and dithiocarbamates (sodium methyl dithiocarbamate, sodium ethyl dithiocarbamate, sodium n-propyl dithiocarbamate, sodium iso-butyl dithiocarbamate, sodium dimethyl dithiocarbamate and sodium diethyl dithiocarbamate) can be successfully determined by visual and potentiometric titrations with standard N-bromosuccinimide in acetonitrile medium. The over all standard deviation calculated from the pooled data of all the visual and potentiometric titrations performed with 10 mg of each compound

were 0.032 and 0.027 (for xanthates) and 0.029 and 0.025 (for dithiocarbamates) respectively. For 40 mg samples, they were 0.067 and 0.046 (for xanthates) and 0.077 and 0.050 (for dithiocarbamates) respectively. Since the results obtained by potentiometric titrations using platinum-antimony electrode assembly agree closely with those obtained by platinum-modified calomel electrode assembly, the former are only recorded in Table I.

The effect of some typical compounds were studied in the titrations of xanthates and dithiocarbamates with N-bromosuccinimide in acetonitrile medium by the recommended procedure in the usual way. No interferences were found from alkyl isothiocyanates, isocyanates, carbon disulphide and urea even when present in upto five fold amounts relative to xanthates and dithiocarbamates.

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